

127. Gould's Belt and the Radcliffe Wave

IT WAS pointed out by John Herschel (1847) that the distribution of bright stars is asymmetric about the Galactic plane. Benjamin Gould (1879) concluded that a prominent group of bright stars was aligned along a great circle at $\sim 20^\circ$ to the Galactic plane. The (expanding) structure has since been known as Gould's Belt, and many later studies of bright stars, OB associations and young clusters have confirmed its existence (e.g. Stothers & Frogel, 1974; Pöppel, 1997; Bobylev, 2014).

In a little more detail, the O–B5 stars, supergiants, associations, young clusters, molecular clouds and star-forming regions within 1 kpc of the Sun populate two flat systems inclined by about 20° . Those of the Galactic belt, aligned nearly along the Milky Way, are characterised by a fairly random distribution in space and age. The Gould Belt, more compressed vertically, hosts most of the O–B2 stars and youngest stellar groups near to the Sun, and has an age of around 30 Myr. It has an ellipsoidal shape with a semi-major axis of about 500 pc and a semi-minor axis of about 340 pc, the Sun being located 150–250 pc off centre.

THE FORMATION of the Gould Belt system remains debated. Suggested origins include collisions of high-velocity clouds with the Galactic disk (Comerón & Torra et al., 1992; 1994); supernova explosions and/or star formation driven by stellar winds originating in the central Cas–Tau association (Olano, 1982; Comerón & Torra, 1994); relation to the Lindblad Ring, an expanding H II feature (Lindblad et al., 1973); a high-speed, oblique collision between a gas cloud of $10^6 M_\odot$ and a dark matter clump of $10^7 M_\odot$ (Bekki, 2009); or simply as a random spatial distribution of a few prominent OB associations (Orion, Perseus OB2, and Scorpius–Centaurus–Lupus) mimicking an ‘inclined belt’ in the sky (Franco et al., 1988; Lépine & Duvert, 1994; Bouy & Alves, 2015).

However, the detailed physical arrangement of these local associations and gas clouds has remained uncertain because the accuracy in distance estimates has been of the same order as their sizes. With the advent of large photometric surveys, and especially with the distances from Gaia, this situation has recently changed.

INDEED, DISTANCES from Gaia appear to offer a somewhat different picture, and support the suggestion, of Bouy & Alves (2015), that the Gould Belt results from a 2D projection effect rather than a physical ring.

Using Gaia DR2, Zari et al. (2018) examined the *three-dimensional* distribution of young stars and star-forming regions within 500 pc of the Sun.

They constructed 3D density maps for early-type (upper-main sequence) stars, and separately for pre-main sequence sources, selected through a combination of photometric and astrometric criteria, including the effects of extinction and reddening. Both show three prominent structures: viz. Scorpius–Centaurus, Orion, and Vela. In addition, the pre-main sequence sources show a number of lower-mass star-forming regions (including Taurus, Perseus, Cepheus, Cassiopeia, and Lacerta) less visible in the upper-main sequence map due to the lack of large numbers of bright, early-type stars.

They found that that younger stars (mainly in Sco–Cen, Orion, Vela, and Taurus) cluster in dense, compact clumps, and are surrounded by older more diffuse sources (such as Cepheus, Cassiopeia, and Lacerta).

Most importantly in this context, they found that the 3D density maps show *no evidence* for the existence of a ring-like Gould Belt structure.

COULD IT REALLY be that, after more than a century of study, Gaia DR2 has ruled that the Gould Belt is nothing more than the arbitrary projection, on the celestial sphere, of a number of nearby star-forming regions? The reality is, unsurprisingly, somewhat more complex.

Let me start with a reference to *The Star Formation Handbook*, a compilation of around 60 of the most important low- and high-mass star-forming regions within 2 kpc of the Sun, distributed across the northern and southern skies (Reipurth, 2008a; Reipurth, 2008b). High-resolution multi-wavelength observations of these nearby regions has provided much of our knowledge of how molecular gas is transformed into stars.

And although accurate distances are critical for understanding the star- and planet-formation processes, distances pre-Gaia were obtained inhomogeneously, and often inaccurately, on a cloud-by-cloud basis.

Using stars in front of, and behind, these complexes, and Gaia-based extinction maps, Zucker et al. (2019; 2020) used Gaia DR2 parallaxes to infer the distances of many of the nearby molecular dust clouds to an accuracy of about 5%. Comparison with distances derived from maser parallax measurements suggests consistent distances with better than 10% scatter for clouds spanning their entire distance range of 150 pc to 2.5 kpc.

DISTANCES of these local cloud complexes were used by Alves et al. (2020) to establish their 3D structure. They found a narrow and coherent 2.7-kpc arrangement of dense gas in the solar neighbourhood, at an angle of about 30° to the Galactic y -axis, running along a significant length of the local (Orion) arm.

The structure comprises the majority of nearby star-forming regions, has an aspect ratio of about 1:20, and contains about $3 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ of gas. While containing many of the clouds associated with the Gould Belt (notably Orion, Perseus, Taurus, and Cepheus), it is also inconsistent with them being part of a physical ‘ring’.

Named by its discoverers at the Radcliffe Institute (Cambridge, MA), this ‘Radcliffe Wave’ is undulating, with its 3D shape well described by a damped sinusoidal wave on the plane of the Milky Way, with an average period of 2 kpc, and a maximum amplitude of 160 pc.

THE RADCLIFFE WAVE has now been confirmed, both in vertical positions and in vertical velocities, by several subsequent studies, and in several different stellar populations.

Having been discovered from the spatial distribution of molecular clouds, Donada & Figueras (2021) examined whether the feature is also present in the *stellar* population. From Gaia DR2 and EDR3, they identified at least 13 young (< 30 Myr) open clusters as probable members of the Radcliffe Wave. They also demonstrated a relationship between their vertical coordinates and vertical velocities, confirming the motion of the wave’s newly born stars as a proxy for its gas motion.

Thulasidharan et al. (2022) extended the studies to OB stars, upper main sequence stars, and red giants, also using Gaia DR2 and EDR3. The wave-like feature has also been confirmed, and its complexity compounded, in the distribution and velocities of very young pre-main-sequence stars (e.g. Bobylev et al., 2022a; Bobylev et al., 2022b; Li & Chen, 2022; Swiggum et al., 2022).

But the fact that the velocity oscillations are not seen in the Gaia data for older stars occupying the same physical volume, appears to exclude an origin attributable to long-lived physical processes (Tu et al., 2022).

THE ORIGIN of the Radcliffe Wave remains a matter of detailed investigation and considerable speculation. Fleck (2020) has suggested that the Radcliffe Wave could be caused by the Kelvin–Helmholtz instability, appearing at the interface between the Galactic disk and the halo rotating at different velocities.

But the majority of studies interpret the wave as arising from a gravitational perturbation of the Galactic disk, due to an external impactor such as a dwarf satellite galaxy of the Milky Way (e.g. Bobylev et al., 2022b).

THE POTENTIAL importance of this Galactic-scale gas feature has been emphasised by Swiggum et al. (2022), where they hypothesise that the Radcliffe Wave constitutes the gas reservoir of the local Orion arm, and therefore a laboratory for studying the interface between Galactic structure, the formation of molecular clouds, and star formation.